

THE INFLUENCE OF POPULAR CULTURE ON THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT AND MORAL RELATIONS IN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

This work examines the importance, main conditions, and methods of raising children in a national spirit within the family. The family is considered the most important environment in shaping a child's personality, where national values, customs, traditions, and moral norms are instilled. National upbringing is an important factor in helping a child develop self-awareness, foster a sense of patriotism, and grow into a socially useful individual. Furthermore, the example set by parents, the family environment, adherence to national traditions, and educational communication play a significant role in the child's spiritual development.

In the current context of globalization, the issue of raising the younger generation in the national spirit is gaining particular relevance. “As a result of the rapid growth of cultural exchange and information flows on a global scale, preserving national values, customs, and traditions and instilling them in the consciousness of the younger generation has become an important task. From this point of view, the issue of national upbringing of children within the family has not only pedagogical but also socio-moral significance” [1]. The family is the first and most important social environment in the formation of personality. It is precisely within the family that a child’s worldview, moral views, and process of understanding national identity begin to take shape. The example set by parents and close relatives, family relationships, and attitudes toward national values play a decisive role in a child’s upbringing. Therefore, it is necessary to create appropriate conditions for properly organizing national upbringing in the family and ensuring its effectiveness.

National upbringing serves to form a sense of patriotism in a child, respect for one’s nation, loyalty to cultural heritage, and a sense of social responsibility. In this process, the spiritual environment in the family, adherence to national traditions, educational communication, and the personal example of parents are among the important factors. The growth of cities, population increase, improvement of living conditions, and cultural and material development contribute to the progress of families and to the comprehensive development of children as mature individuals. Although the number of large families has been decreasing compared with the past, this tendency has not completely lost its significance. Our hardworking people did not say without reason: “A house with children is like a

marketplace; a house without children is like a graveyard.” It is no secret that in the Central Asian republics, including Uzbekistan, the transition from large families to families with three or four children, and later to one or two children, has been increasing year by year.

From a pedagogical point of view, raising an only child makes education more difficult, since the only child in the family often grows up as the “living toy,” pride, beloved child, and favorite of adults. Let us analyze what negative consequences this may lead to. First, from a social and psychological perspective, childlessness or having few children can weaken the stability of the family. Most divorces in our republic occur in families with no children or few children. Second, studies in the field of medicine and anthropogenic factors indicate that children who are able to overcome life difficulties are often the second or third child in the family. Limiting the family to only one child may lead to an increase in poorly developed personalities in the future. As A.S. Makarenko emphasized, “It can be firmly stated that raising an only son or daughter is much more difficult than raising several children. Even if there are certain material difficulties, one should not be satisfied with having only one child.”

“If mutual assistance and trust exist in the family, then in such a family a sincere, kind person who is always ready to help friends will grow up. In families of people who embody the qualities of a well-mannered person, peace, comfort, and sincere respect always prevail. Observations show that young people have a strong need to build relationships with adults” [2]. From this perspective, children raised in peaceful and harmonious families take as an example such positive qualities existing in the family as politeness, good manners, respect for elders, care for others, mutual respect among family members, and especially care shown toward women. Indeed, the family is an extremely important primary group that advances social life, educates the future generation, and bears responsibility for their development. The family is built on the basis of full equality between men and women and their equal responsibility for the family.

“The growth of family income, on the one hand, contributes to the improvement of parents’ intellectual level and cultural life, and on the other hand, positively influences the formation of higher spiritual needs among family members, the improvement and enrichment of family relations, and the content of communication between adults and children” [3]. As life shows, harmony between family education and social education can be ensured only through the promotion of knowledge related to upbringing. Therefore, in order to organize family life correctly from an educational point of view, educators and the wider public should assist the population through pedagogical and psychological knowledge and develop a system for providing parents with educational knowledge.

As proven in the studies of pedagogical scholars, the effectiveness of upbringing increases if work related to family education is carried out under the following conditions:

1. If the school consistently directs the totality of its educational influences toward the process of family upbringing;
2. If the teaching staff properly organizes its mature pedagogical and educational requirements in cooperation with the family;
3. If teachers begin guiding family education before children enter school and continue this work regularly.

Cooperation among the family, school, and the public is one of the urgent issues of today. This is because, “firstly, cooperation among the family, school, and the public in family education is itself a complex process, in which, in addition to existing problems, representatives of communities and trade unions also participate. Secondly, parents and relatives are representatives of various labor collectives and discuss factors related to the spiritual lives of their friends and acquaintances, as well as their attitudes toward life, industry, and family responsibilities” [4]. For this reason, children raised in such families evaluate their own parents by observing the activities of other parents in the street and in public places.

In Uzbekistan, the highest goal of social education is to form in every citizen the qualities characteristic of a perfect person. By a perfect person, we mean an individual who has a high level of consciousness, is capable of independent thinking, serves as an example to others through their behavior, and is knowledgeable. At the present stage, there are specific features, regularities, opportunities, and mechanisms of raising children [5]. It should be emphasized separately that applying educational and upbringing measures while fully taking into account children’s individual characteristics helps eliminate misunderstandings in interpersonal relations and creates a warm psychological climate.

At present, the issue of children’s future is becoming extremely important. Childhood is distinguished by imitateness, the incomplete formation of a stable point of view, emotionality, and courage. Therefore, special attention should be paid to boys and girls who are easily influenced by external factors. The main reasons for the need to increase attention to children’s issues may be identified as follows:

1. Changes in culture, industry, literature, and socio-economic conditions as a result of the development of science and technology;
2. The increase in children’s level of awareness due to the expansion of mass media;
3. The awareness of boys and girls of world events;
4. The acceleration of their physical and intellectual development;
5. The need for a special approach to ideological, political, patriotic, and international education in working with young people;
6. The deep penetration of the issues of openness, social justice, and democracy into social life.

In the education system of the republic, broad opportunities have been created for students to acquire knowledge independently, think creatively, manage themselves, understand, evaluate, and control their own activities. “Along with sharp changes in psychological processes among young people, shifts are also observed in their mental activity” [5]. Therefore, significant life changes occur in interpersonal relations, in communication between students and teachers, and in interactions between adults and children. Difficulties arise in the process of these changes. First of all, they appear in the educational process: the forms, style, and methods of presenting new information no longer satisfy young people.

Due to the emergence of a personal point of view among young people, they try to assert their own opinions despite the concern and criticism of adults. Irritability becomes an inseparable part of daily behavior. “Some educators speak with concern, criticize certain negative traits, and try to identify their socio-psychological roots; however, they are unable to

develop a system of measures and actions to prevent these shortcomings” [6]. Existing conflicts and contradictions can be gradually overcome by ensuring psychological maturity, complicating types of activity, and forming new psychological qualities in the child’s personality.

In conclusion, raising children in the national spirit within the family is a complex and multifaceted process that is of great importance for the development and stability of society. In this process, the family appears as the main educational environment and plays a decisive role in the formation of the child as a personality. It is precisely within the family that national values, customs, traditions, and moral norms are deeply instilled in the child’s consciousness.

Research shows that the effectiveness of national upbringing is directly connected, first of all, with the spiritual environment in the family, the personal example of parents, adherence to national traditions, and the establishment of effective educational communication with the child. If a healthy psychological environment is created in the family and upbringing is carried out consistently and purposefully, a child develops a high level of national self-awareness, a sense of patriotism, spiritual maturity, and social activity. In addition, in raising children in the national spirit, it is important to improve parents’ pedagogical literacy, harmonize national values with modern approaches, and ensure consistency in the educational process. Thus, by properly organizing national upbringing in the family, it is possible to raise spiritually mature, nationally proud, and socially active individuals for society.

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